

8. A. B. P. LEVER and D. OGDEN, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 2041.
 9. C. A. AGAMBAR, P. ANASTREY and K. G. ORRELL, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton*, 1974, 964.

Studies in Fe(III) 6, 7-Dihydroxy-Naphthalene-2-Sulphonic Acid Complexes

M. L. NARWADE, S. W. SATHE and M. V. KARBELKAR

Department of Chemistry, Vidarbha Mahavidyalaya,
Amaravati

Manuscript received 2 November 1977, revised 24 April 1979,
accepted 19 May 1980

SULPHONIC acids are known to form coloured complexes with Fe(III). Mc.Bryde⁸ has studied Fe(III) complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline-7-sulphonic acid spectrophotometrically. Recently Narwade⁹ has investigated the interaction of transitional metal ions with sulphonic acids.

A preliminary experiment with solutions containing Fe(III) perchlorate ($1 \times 10^{-1} M$) and sodium salt of 6-7 dihydroxy-naphthalene-2-sulphonic acid (6, 7 DHN-2SA), ($20 \times 10^{-2} M$) and free $HClO_4$ showed colour change from dark-blue, violet and then to orange when pH was varied from 2 to 8. This indicated the presence of more than one complex species in solution. A potentiometric study was undertaken to determine the stability constants of complexes of Fe(III) with 6, 7 DHN-2SA. Spectrophotometric study was made with a limited aim to confirm the result of potentiometry.

Experimental

Potentiometry: The experimental procedure involved the Calvin-Bjerrum titrations of three carbonate-free mixtures: (1) Free $HClO_4$ ($1.002 \times 10^{-2} M$), (2) Free $HClO_4$ (1.002×10^{-2}) + 6, 7 DHN-2SA ($20.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) and (3) Free $HClO_4$ ($1.002 \times 10^{-2} M$) + 6, 7 DHN-2SA + Ferric perchlorate ($4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$). All the mixtures were titrated separately with 0.1818M NaOH solution in a double walled titration vessel with a seal on water jacket at a temperature of $25 \pm 0.2^\circ$. Total volume was 50 ml each time. The ionic strength of 0.1M was maintained constant by adding $NaClO_4$ solution. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through the assembly containing the electrodes in order to exclude CO_2 .

pH measurements were made with a ELICO pH Meter (accuracy ± 0.05 unit) using glass and calomel electrodes.

From the shifts in the pH titration curves the values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL , were calculated by Irving and Rossotti's method.

Results and Discussion

The acid+ligand curve was found to be coinciding with the acid curve upto pH 6.0 (Fig. 1). This was expected as the ligand 6, 7 DHN-2SA was taken in the form of its sodium salt. In water, the salt dissociates into sodium ion and ionic ligand (H_2L^-). The sulphonic acid is a good chelating agent and is highly acidic due to its $-SO_3H$ group. The dissociation equilibria can be represented as under:

From the plot of \bar{n}_A vs pH (Fig. 1a) pK values were determined. The pK_1 (first dissociation constant of $-OH$ group) at $\bar{n}_A=1.5$, which was found 8.10, be ascribed to the $-OH$ group in the 6th position,

Fig. 1(a)

because the overall electron withdrawing effect of the $-SO_3^-$ group is efficiently transferred to the 6-hydroxy group. The hydrogen bonding between the pentoxide ion of 6th position and the $-OH$ group at the 7th position would increase the dissociation constant of the $-OH$ group in 7th position leading to a higher value of pK_2 (second dissociation constant of $-OH$ group). The accurate pK_2 value could not be determined due to the limited accuracy of glass electrode above pH 11.0. Actual titrations are carried out above pH 12.0. The value of pK_2 corresponding to the pH, where $\bar{n}_A=0.5$

could not be found by this method. The value of pK_3 for $-OH$ group was calculated by the expression—

$$2pH = pK_1 + pK_2 \text{ and from the } \bar{n}_A = 1$$

Knowledge of pK_1 : The value of pK_2 was found out to be 10.4. Kabadi *et al*⁵ have determined the values of pK_2 of salicylaldehyde and salicylic acid by using above expression.

The deviation of (acid+ligand+metal ion) curve from the (free acid+ligand) curve was observed from pH 2.0. Precipitation was not observed upto pH 9.0. This observation together with the fact that concentrations employed were low, excluded factors like hydrolysis of Fe(III) and presence of polynuclear hydrogen and hydroxyl bearing complexes. This facilitated the calculation of stability constants of the complexes. The colour of solution was dark blue upto pH 3.0, orange above pH 7.0 and violet in the intermediate pH range. The departure of metal complex titration curve from the reagent (ligand) titration curve was observed at pH less than 2.0. This clearly indicated that Fe(III) forms 1 : 1 complex below pH 2.0. The maximum value of \bar{n}

Fig. 1(b)

was found to be 2.9 indicating the presence of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complex formations in solution. The values of pL at \bar{n} 0.5, 1.5, 2.5 [Fig. 1(b)] were utilised to calculate the metal-ligand stability constants. The values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ were found 18.10, 12.40, 8.00 respectively. The reported² values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes with 6, 7 DHN-2SA are 13.01 and 10.73; and 10.52 and 6.23 respectively. The sulphonic acid complexes of Fe(III) ion are more stable than Cu(II) and Ni(II), because Fe(III) is expected to be a hard acid.

Spectrophotometry :

For confirming the formation of complexes of Fe(III) with 6, 7 DHN-2SA, the method due to Varielle⁴ was employed. Various solutions of metal ion and ligand in the ratio of 1 : 20 were prepared in the pH range of 2.0 to 8.0. The ionic strength of each solution was maintained at 0.1M by adding NaClO₄ solution. The spectra were recorded by AIMIL Spectrochem(PEI). The curves were constructed by plotting optical density of complex against wavelength in nm (Fig. 2). The curves were

FIG. 2.

found to intersect at two isobestic points corresponding to wavelength of 520 nm and 56 nm respectively. This existence of the two isobestic points indicated the presence of three different complex species in the pH range of 2.0 to 8.0. The curve below pH 2.5 did not pass through any of the isobestic points. It could be concluded that below pH 2.5 the solution contained exclusive 1 : 1 complex.

Acknowledgement

Our sincere thanks are due to Principal, Vidarbha Mahavidyalaya, Amaravati for providing all facilities.

References

1. W. A. E. MC. BRYDE, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 1917.
2. M. L. NARWADE, Ph. D. Thesis, Marathwada University, Aurangabad, Oct., 1974.
3. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3367.

4. L. VARIELLE, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1955, 870.
 5. M. B. KABADI, K. B. JABALPURWALA and K. A. VENTAKA CHALAM, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* 1964, 26, 1011.

Thermodynamic Studies of Cr(II), Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Chelates of *o*-(*N*- α -furfuralideneimino) Benzene Sulphonic Acid

C. P. GUPTA, N. K. SANKHLA, K. G. SHARMA
and

R. K. MEHTA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur,
Jodhpur (India)

Manuscript received 21 August 1978, revised 4 March 1980,
accepted 13 May 1980

A perusal of the literature^{1,2} shows that no systematic study has been made on the bivalent metal chelates of *o*-(*N*- α -furfuralideneimino) benzene sulphonic acid (HFB), hence the same was undertaken. The findings of these studies are reported in the present paper.

Experimental

Metal salt used were of BDH AnalaR quality. Furfuraldehyde and orthanilic acid (L. R.) supplied by Fluka were used. Precision pH-meter type OP : 205 No. 837 (Radelkis) equipped with a glass-calomel electrode assembly was used at 25°, 35° and 45° ($\mu=0.01, 0.05$ and $0.1M$ NaClO₄). HFB was synthesised from furfuraldehyde and orthanilic acid by the method reported earlier³. It gave satisfactory elemental analyses. The titrations were

carried out in presence and in absence of the metal ions, against carbonate free 0.01M NaOH in accordance with Calvin's extension of Bjerrum method^{4,5}.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves it is observed that the metal-ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curve which suggests that liberation of proton occurs due to complexation. The pK_1 of HFB as determined by interpolation at half \bar{n} values and algebraic method⁶ was 5.95, 5.77 and 5.60 at 25°, 35° and 45°. Thus the pK values fall with rise of temperature. These values suggest that HFB is a monoprotic ligand. The metal-ligand stability constants were read from the formation curves drawn by plotting \bar{n} vs $-\log[A^-]$. The refinement was done by various computational method⁷, such as correction term, convergence formula successive approximation and interpolation at various \bar{n} values methods and their average value ($\log \beta_2$) along with their deviations from the theoretical values are summarised in Table 1. The $\log \beta_2$ values of the metal chelates are in the order Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) > Fe(II) > Mn(II) > Cr(II) which is in accordance with the Irving-William rule⁸.

The thermodynamic stability constants ($\log K^\circ$) as shown in Table 1 have been obtained by extrapolation of measured formation constants to zero ionic strength from graph between \log of stability constant vs $\sqrt{\mu}$, where μ is the ionic strength.

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been evaluated using Gibbs-Helmholtz equation⁹, (Table 1). The ΔG of all the chelates have more

TABLE 1—AVERAGE STABILITY CONSTANTS, THEIR DEVIATIONS* FROM THEORETICAL VALUES AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF THE BIVALENT METAL CHELATES OF *o*-(*N*- α -FURFURALIDENEIMINO) BENZENE SULPHONIC ACID AT 25°, 35° AND 45°

Metal	Stability constant ($\mu=0.1M$ NaClO ₄)			$\log K^\circ$			$-\Delta G$ K cal/mole			ΔH K cal/mole 35°	ΔS cal/deg/mole at 35°	
	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°			
Cr(II)	$\log K_1$	3.68	3.75	3.78								
	$\log K_2$	2.70	2.82	2.95	7.00	7.20	7.40	9.03	9.40	10.03	15.18	80.23
	$\log \beta_2$	6.38 ± 0.02	6.57 ± 0.05	6.73 ± 0.03								
Mn(II)	$\log K_1$	3.86	3.96	4.06								
	$\log K_2$	3.02	3.24	3.47	8.25	8.60	8.70	9.49	10.26	10.94	14.09	78.89
	$\log \beta_2$	6.88 ± 0.04	7.20 ± 0.02	7.53 ± 0.01								
Fe(II)	$\log K_1$	3.96	4.05	4.15								
	$\log K_2$	3.16	3.35	3.54	8.45	8.75	9.00	9.82	10.50	11.19	12.30	74.01
	$\log \beta_2$	7.12 ± 0.03	7.40 ± 0.04	7.69 ± 0.04								
Co(II)	$\log K_1$	4.23	4.37	4.66*								
	$\log K_2$	3.45	3.63	3.81	9.05	9.35	9.70	10.59	11.45	12.32	17.13	92.76
	$\log \beta_2$	7.68 ± 0.02	8.00 ± 0.04	8.47 ± 0.02								
Ni(II)	$\log K_1$	4.41	4.51	4.61								
	$\log K_2$	3.77	4.01	4.25	9.30	9.65	9.95	11.28	12.08	12.89	14.74	87.06
	$\log \beta_2$	8.18 ± 0.05	8.52 ± 0.02	8.86 ± 0.01								
Cu(II)	$\log K_1$	4.80	4.86	4.93								
	$\log K_2$	4.19	4.35	4.57	10.00	10.20	10.50	12.28	13.08	13.81	21.67	112.7
	$\log \beta_2$	8.99 ± 0.03	9.21 ± 0.01	9.49 ± 0.04								

* Very small deviations (0.01-0.05) were observed.